

Transformative resistance for a just and inclusive European Green Deal

Insights and policy recommendations from the ACCTING project

February 2025

The global climate crisis disproportionately affects marginalised and vulnerable populations, who bear the brunt of its ecological, economic, and social impacts. Yet these groups are not merely victims; they are key drivers of transformative change. Their practices of resistance, resilience, and sustainability provide vital, untapped resources for addressing the climate crisis and fostering social and behavioural shifts toward sustainability. Their resistance and resilience, often seen as barriers, should thus instead be recognised as sources of innovation. This requires agency of these communities and incorporating their contributions into policy decision-making processes. By centring on the voices and lived experiences of those most affected, policymakers can design inclusive strategies that address both climate justice and social equity.

Recommendations

The recommendations below are directed towards policymakers. They highlight the importance of acknowledging the perspectives of marginalised groups, learning from their inspiring experiences and practices of resistance, resilience and sustainability, and understanding them as sources and agents of change for generating better policy.

Acknowledging and understanding resistance

1. **Policymakers need to acknowledge and understand resistance within its unique context.** This involves being open to new notions, sites and agents of resistance, while engaging with and avoiding stereotypical and stagnant views of resistant communities. It is also important to be perceptive to the cases of resistance in different parts of Europe i.e., both the North and the South.
2. Policymakers can explore the vulnerabilities and the positions of the resisting actors; use their insights to map **power** relationships in a certain context; and aim to understand the complex **agencies** of disadvantaged groups. While resisting groups can rally behind a common agenda, existing power relations within groups might determine the terms and directions of the resistance, leading to silencing of more complex and intersectional positions within the resistance. Furthermore, resistance can emerge from perceived, experienced, or expected vulnerabilities; the varieties in the context of resistance can **illuminate the roots of resistance**. Policymakers can collaborate with researchers and civil society organisations to unravel these complexities of resistance.

Engaging with resistance

3. Policymakers can approach resistance as a call for 'better' platforms to enhance dialogue and policy co-design. Actors can resist the existing participatory mechanisms, finding them exclusive to privileged actors, disagreeing with the general course of action, or seeing them being implemented only for box-ticking purposes. **Policymakers can**

establish permanent platforms for dialogue and policy co-design between stakeholders and ensure their inclusivity and sustainability. To avoid “top-downness” in such platforms, it is important to identify the most resistant civil society actors and communities, involving and/or engaging them in the process.

- 4. Policymakers can employ various tools for facilitation, conflict resolution, and dialogue-building to navigate those processes being slowed down by resistance, and to ensure the voluntary inclusion of marginalised groups.** Stakeholders can bring in facilitator expertise to implement methods, such as deep democracy, indigenous method of circle process, participatory action, nonviolent communication and many others, and standardise diverse engagement mechanisms, such as local hearing groups, to ensure the inclusion of resisting marginalised groups. When the process encounters obstacles or stagnation, it is crucial to remain patient, flexible, and open to innovative solutions. By viewing tensions as opportunities for untapped potential and valuable insights, policymakers can foster mutual transformation and growth.
- 5. Policymakers can engage with resisting marginalised communities and people by leveraging their networks, resources, and wisdom, thereby amplifying their role as agents of change.**

Disadvantaged communities often possess valuable social, cultural, and political networks, along with strong solidarity and safety nets. To tap into these resources, policymakers can commit to long-term engagement with the communities, including multiple site visits, paying specific attention to gender+ dynamics and ensuring visits include women’s spaces. It is important to adapt to the communities’ schedules and conditions, to foster effective collaboration.

- 6. Policy can channel resistance into a path for community empowerment.** Resistance is sometimes based on unequal access to information, knowledge and confidence to navigate new situations. When policymakers, researchers, and civil society organisations run projects based on community empowerment, capacity-building, or community resilience, these projects become potential sites for engaging with resistance.
- 7. Policymakers can also learn from the disadvantaged groups who do not resist and ask: whose voice is missing?** Policies can always be improved. While it is easy to engage with the most vocal groups, other communities who suffer the consequences may remain unheard. To reach these groups, policymakers can deploy targeted strategies, such as consulting associations representing marginalised groups early in the policy development

process — even if these groups are not directly related to the policy’s environmental focus, such as migrant associations.

Transforming resistance

8. Policymakers can identify hotspots, where sustainability transitions and transformations are likely to lead to tensions between social and environmental concerns. Pre-existing axes of inequality often shape vulnerability and disadvantage. Insights gained from resistance can **contribute to long-term solutions to complex matters such as human rights and social equity, cultural heritage protection, and safety from natural hazards**. By fostering alliances between civil society organisations and bottom-up experiences, policymakers can strengthen different causes.

Findings from ACCTING

The ACCTING project builds on large-scale European interdisciplinary research to address the complexities of behavioural and social change and find solutions for equitable and sustainable climate transitions. In the research, resistance manifests in diverse forms: as visible, organised, collective actions; and as subtle every day and unorganised forms, such as hesitation, noncompliance, or disengagement:

- Marginalised groups frequently criticise top-down policies, especially when these policies are experienced as diminishing their agency and insights, resulting in further distrust of the authorities. **Marginalised groups also find the few existing consultation and collaboration mechanisms merely procedural**, rather than having any concrete and substantial impact.

***Example:** In Türkiye, where wildfires are increasing, a policy regulating civic participation in fire intervention was changed to accommodate volunteers into the existing mechanisms. However, this policy change downgraded the local forest villagers' role in fire prevention and intervention. Feeling that their efforts were not recognised as valuable, the forest villagers started experiencing friction with the authorities, such as not showing willingness to support the fire intervention teams, or demanding more recruitment possibilities for the villagers in the firefighting teams.*

***Example:** In Norway's green energy transition, authorities carried out consultation sessions. However, disadvantaged groups perceived them as merely performative rather than genuine, as authorities seemed to not engage with the community's input. This led to frustration and a sense of neglect in the community.*

- Resistance is particularly common against sustainable transportation policies. Modal shift policies aim to benefit all, **yet the measures implemented tend to disproportionately affect marginalised communities** in the areas that lack efficient public transport. As a result, such measures tend to be seen as top-down and disruptive by these communities.

***Example:** In Italy, policies restricting private car use by creating Green Belt/Low Emission Zones have sparked protests in a disadvantaged neighbourhood in Rome. Allowing only low-emission vehicles in certain areas and imposing fines on others leaves marginalised groups in a challenging conundrum: an overcrowded and unreliable public transport system, which increases the dependence of marginalised residents on private transportation.*

***Example:** In Norway, removing parking spaces for new bike lanes has raised concerns for those with physical or mental health challenges, fearing it would disrupt their routines, as they often rely on personal vehicles.*

- ACCTING’s gender+ perspective ensured a concerted attention to gendered norms, ideals and stereotypes, which have been found to underpin passive forms of resistance – such as avoidance, hesitance, and nonengagement (Stewart et al., 2021). Yet, **sustainability transitions often fail to consider existing gender norms that affect and constrain women and LGBTQI+ people’s lives**, leading to avoidance without overt confrontation.

***Example:** In Italy, women especially those with caregiving responsibilities and migrant women with larger families, face challenges in transitioning to cycling. Their resistance is not to the policies per se but related to the burdens of care work and safety concerns. Many women also report fears of harassment and inappropriate comments as reasons for their reluctance to cycle.*

- ACCTING research identifies **resistance caused by the seemingly incompatible differences between modern governance mechanisms and the nomadic, indigenous, pastoralist and other groups living in/with nature**. Despite the increasing relevance of these groups for sustainable transition and transformation, authorities resist considering new perspectives brought by such groups and their lifestyles, dismissing them as “traditional”, “primitive,” or “anti-modern”. Integrating equity and equality concerns into policy planning requires a thorough review of existing systems, and more radical interventions towards sustainability, when necessary.

Better Stories

In ACCTING we use ‘*better stories*’, a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis¹, to refer to promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices. We have identified potential platforms or spaces for dialogue, co-creation, and collaboration with/in communities enacted by both individuals and collectives. Below we put forward examples from ACCTING’s research on the importance of the presence of community networks to identify and engage resistance.

- In **Italy**, the representatives from the Civil Protection Agency worked with a network of “cultural mediators” who would know the locations of the vulnerable individuals and facilitate connections with them during a disaster situation. Thanks to these mediators, the Agency drew a rough map of the vulnerabilities in the area, which was integrated into disaster intervention plans.
- In **Hungary**, following a mayor’s failed compensation practices after a flood, civil forums were organised to articulate collective resentment. These platforms brought together different experiences of floods and made them visible, which eventually supported improvements in the management of floods.
- By contrast, also in **Hungary**, some local platforms established for biodiversity conservation initiatives lacked community-based decision-making mechanisms. This discouraged some local people’s active engagement as they were sceptical about how decisions were taken in these platforms. Yet, when residents, farmers, and state agencies united, they started creating a sense of community, made new knowledge being accounted for in decisions, and sceptical individuals eventually came to appreciate these platforms.
- In **Türkiye**, residents of the Ahmetler village located in a remote mountain forest in the Mediterranean, resisted orders to evacuate due to a growing forest fire. The predominantly older, female villagers knew specific ways in which they could support the fire intervention efforts. A receptive forest engineer who arrived at the site and recognised the villagers’ geographical understanding, permitted them to help in the fire response -- and this eventually played a crucial role in stopping the spread of the fire.
- In **Portugal** the CICLOPES² initiative tackles resistance to sustainable mobility by tackling financial barriers, lack of skills, and low confidence – commons sources of such resistance. It does so through a community-centred approach that fosters inclusivity, empowerment, and skills development in disadvantaged communities. The initiative offers free bike

¹ [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.](#)

² <https://ciclopes.pt/>

rentals, making cycling a viable option, and it also reduces resistance by offering training, equipping participants with the skills and confidence to ride safely.

- In **Austria**, refugees in the *Garten der Begegnung*³ faced a cultural disconnect with the food provided in asylum centres, which did not align with their dietary habits or preferences. In response, they sought alternative ways to access and produce familiar foods, turning to community gardens to grow traditional vegetables that were unavailable in local markets.
- In **Türkiye**, the Izmir Municipality's policy of opening urban gardens in a historically neglected and disadvantaged neighbourhood was met with hesitation and resistance, largely by the migrants and refugee inhabitants. However, the municipal staff organised community gardening and gender-awareness activities, child-care facilities, and long-term community engagements for the women and children of the neighbourhood. This resulted in the women supporting the gardens and expressing a sense of empowerment.

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³ <https://www.gartenderbegegnung.com/>

About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

Running until May 2025 and based on two research cycles, ACCTING mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal, focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies.

Find out more about the project and discover more factsheets at <https://accting.eu>

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Infographics: YW. Layout: ESF.

Acknowledgment and disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036504. The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of its authors and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.